

Forms, Methods and Means of using Public Speaking in the Process of Pedagogical Activity

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Abstract. *Every student studying at a higher educational institution should be able to freely express their opinion in public. If this is not normal, that is, a student cannot speak at seminars, defense of scientific papers, and even at spiritual and educational events, then it indicates a speech deficit. Existing practical experience of teachers of pedagogical disciplines, as well as individual training in the didactics of higher education institutions theoretical provisions on the methodology of teaching pedagogy, principles, rules, and recommendations have been systematized.*

Keywords: *spiritual and educational, emphasis, pause, get used to thinking, why, for what purpose.*

In this regard, we believe it is appropriate to cite the recommendations of the renowned professor, scientist, and orator R. Zhumaniyazov, which made it possible for the speaker's speech to be free from logical and speech defects. **These are:**

1. Read the text expressively, following the stress and pause. (eyebrow reading, inside reading, rereading, reading aloud and reading)
2. Understanding the meaning of the word in the text and the content of the sentence. (Find out and understand what's going on)
3. The main goal of the text is to understand to whom and to what the call is directed. Approach the text with questions about why, why, why, for what purpose. (A poorly diagnosed patient is difficult to treat. To have a summary of the idea and the owner of the idea).
4. Summarize your factual information and comments in the sense of confirmation or negation related to the addition, enrichment, and interpretation of this opinion. Also be interested in other people's opinions on this matter. (Get used to thinking rather than thinking. Do not deviate from the main idea, from the text.)
5. During the interpretation of the idea in the text, connect, compare, and justify the relevant or controversial, controversial aspects with the information you have heard, seen, known, and read. Explain the relevance and relevance of the idea with real-life examples.
6. Draw a final conclusion about the text. Place them in a sequential order. Check once again whether the evidence is reliable and scientific. (Feel and imagine that an entire team is waiting for you behind a stand, a microphone, and a video camera.)
7. Practice speaking in front of a mirror at home or at work. (It is only a hard exercise that allows the climber to climb a rock. The speaker achieves his goal, his idea through attracting public attention and speaking skills.)

8. Before going to the podium, perform breathing exercises, voice exercises, and take a final look at the speech being spoken. (Before speaking, it is necessary to sleep well, rest, and eat normally.)
9. Of course, be interested in who the speech is aimed at. (Adapting the tone of speech to take into account the audience's age, profession, gender, level of knowledge and worldview.)
10. Put your clothes in order, comb your hair, and check your face and eyes for a moment. Remember that a spot on your shirt, a tie tied incorrectly, and a buttoned-down suit will affect your speech.
11. The speaker stands at the altar. Coming to the team in a good mood with bold steps, looking at them with a half-smile, putting the right hand on their chest, nodding and greeting. (They look to you, and they look to your word. Word is a mirror of human identity.)
12. It is not about what to talk about, but about how to talk about it. (The question is not how to start, but how to start. Whether it's a word or a thought, it's not. The need to attract public attention with the first word or situation. Occasionally, the skillful use of an interesting anecdote, narration, or poem in its own way.)
13. Hold yourself loosely, don't cringe, breathe well, don't relax, don't get excited. Visualize your audience as your loved ones. (They are buyers. Your market will fail if you don't have the products you want.)
14. Do not use foreign words and dialectal elements that are foreign to the literary language. Make your speech simple, concise, clear, logical, and effective. Use popular, everyone-understanding words and phrases. (It is the artist's fault that he cannot entertain the audience with pleasure.)

Follow the speech technique thoroughly and correctly. Speak clearly, clearly, without gnawing at the sounds. Expressive means such as diction, intonation, stress, pause, rhythm are signs of speech effectiveness. (The clarity of speech is due to the clarity of thought, the clarity of thought is due to the clarity of pronunciation. He won't sit in a broken chair.)

15. When speaking, pay close attention to the audience, be vigilant and perspicacious. If they don't listen to you, it's not they, it's you! (Do not invite guests without filling the tablecloth, you will be embarrassed. The hunter does not shoot without aiming at the prey. His goal is not to empty the ammunition, but to capture the prey. The speaker has a loaded rifle, he needs a badge, all he needs is to press the trigger.)
16. It is also important to listen to public opinion and debate. This not only brings you closer to your audience, but also contributes to a deeper understanding of the topic.

When speaking, it is necessary to avoid scratching the throat, unnecessarily shrugging your shoulders, pulling your nose, coughing, using repetitive parasitic words such as "haligi," "ösha," "anaqa," "demak," "nimaydi," as well as "tak," "znachit," "i," "toys." Do not speak quickly or slowly, it is advisable to speak at a certain pace by attracting the listener's attention, using different voice timbers in moderation. (No one's following you.). While completing the topic, be interested in the result, look in the eyes of the listeners. Only the eyes give a true assessment. There is flattery in the "word" of the language. The eye is an exception to the word. Therefore, both anger and love are in the eyes. It will be very useful for you to get acquainted with the thoughts and concepts of the listeners on the topic in your next speech, to be free from speech defects.

Students typically have two types of speech disorders.

1. Congenital stuttering, inability to pronounce some letters, and omission of letters when speaking quickly.
2. Acquired speechlessness is shyness or fear of speaking, timidity.

The first of these shortcomings is a biological factor, while the second is a direct psychological factor. First, let's consider the origin of medical speech defects. Usually, the student must choose the words necessary to express their opinion. Then he must connect them based on the rules of language

grammar and pronounce them through the articulation of speech organs. However, many students experience instances of incomprehensible and meaningful speech, non-compliance with the accuracy and correctness of the actions of the speech members. If we analyze speech disorders and defects in students from a physiological perspective, we can cite a number of reasons.

Specifically:

1. The presence of physical impairments or hereditary diseases in the womb of students.
2. Adult indifference to the development of students' speech apparatus in childhood.
3. The fact that the students have received physical damage to the tongue-controlling part of the brain to this day.

Now we will present the psychological reasons for the speech deficiencies of students.

1. Fear of something in youth.
2. Incorrect pronunciation of words.
3. Non-socialization.
4. Speaking another language at a young age and learning another language when you grow up.
5. Being ashamed of speaking in front of people, isolation.
6. Defects caused by deliberate non-speech to someone or something.

There are also social flaws in students' speech, and it is impossible not to acknowledge them. **These include:**

1. The use of slang and borrowed words in the language.
2. Speech distortion: pause, use of unnecessary words.
3. Inability to fully express one's opinion, etc.

To eliminate these shortcomings, each student must first work on themselves.

Therefore, we believe in a fundamentally new approach to teaching pedagogy methodological approach to teaching pedagogy We have considered the foundations of the pedagogical course. It allows us to move on to describing the structure and content. This is next will be discussed in the section. The methodology of teaching pedagogical disciplines through advanced training. teachers are well-versed in the theory and practice of pedagogy acquiring rich historical and educational experience modern professional, spiritual, moral, reative and productive qualities provides practical assistance in the formation.

Used literature:

1. Alimuhamedov. A. "Antik adabiyot tarixi", T.: O'qituvchi, 1969 y. 199-bet
2. Bekmirzayev Norqul. Nutq madanyati va notiqlik asoslari (*O'quv qo'llanma*) Toshkent O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyas "Fan" nashriyoti 2007
3. Sitseron "Notiqlik san'ati" O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi nashriyoti. Toshkent. 2018-yil.